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ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF UKRAINE'S EUROPEAN INTEGRATION

Анотація. В роботі розглянуті актуальні питання забезпечення якості вищої освіти в Україні, розкриті основні принципи та чинники впливу на рівень освіти. Авторами досліджені особливості впровадження механізмів забезпечення якості вищої освіти з урахуванням сучасних умов сьогодення та модернізації навчально-освітнього процесу в ЗВО. Проаналізовано американську модель вищої освіти та досліджені особливості світової пріоритетності їх системи освіти. Визначені шляхи підвищення якості вищої освіти в Україні на базі інтеграції освітнього простору.

Ключові слова: вища освіта, навчально-освітній процес, модернізація, освітній простір.

Abstract. The paper deals with topical issues of quality assurance of higher education in Ukraine, reveals the basic principles and factors influencing the level of education. The authors investigate the peculiarities of implementing mechanisms for ensuring the quality of higher education, taking into account the current conditions and modernization of the educational process in higher education institutions. The American model of higher education is analyzed and the peculiarities of the world priority of their education system are studied. The ways of improving the quality of higher education in Ukraine on the basis of integration of educational space are determined.

Keywords: higher education, educational process, modernization, educational space.

Statement of the problem and its relevance. Today, the problems and challenges that arise in the educational process have become an incredible challenge for the higher education system in Ukraine. Insufficient funding of the higher education system, irrational use of resources, insufficient autonomy of the higher education institution management system, inequality of social responsibility of the higher education institution, lack of capacity to generate and commercialize intellectual products, unlimited manifestations of academic dishonesty, imperfect mechanisms for assessing learning outcomes, non-compliance with European education standards – all this leads to a decrease in the quality of competencies of students and interaction with the public. At present, the above problems have not lost their relevance, but have only intensified, because in the context of the war in Ukraine, one of the main tasks of the state is to ensure quality higher education. Therefore, the education system requires the introduction of a systematic mechanism for taking into account the principles of sustainable

development in the process of ensuring the quality of higher education, effective interaction of all participants in the educational process and effective tools.

Analysis of the main studies and publications. The study of the problems of modernization of the educational process is devoted to the articles [1, p. 6–22; 2, p. 54–59]. The issue of ensuring the quality of higher education is covered in publications [3; 4, p. 141–145]. Despite the existence of a significant range of studies related to the problems of educational process development, ensuring a high professional level of competencies of participants in educational activities today remains the most important problem of forming high-quality higher education [5, p. 24–36]. Moreover, the quality of higher education needs to be modernized, based on the formation of modern competencies of students of higher education institutions and the compliance of their learning outcomes with the requirements of employers today.

Presentation of the main material. During the full-scale war in Ukraine, the educational process has undergone changes: a different learning format, taking into account security circumstances, the development of individual educational trajectories of students, reorganization of the structure and dismissal of the teaching staff of higher education institutions. In addition, the destruction of educational institutions and social infrastructure, business relocation and migration, instability of the situation and danger to citizens have had a negative impact on the participants of the educational process and led to a deterioration in the ability to provide training and a decrease in the quality of higher education. After all, the quality of higher education depends on many factors, among which the following should be highlighted:

- destruction of educational institutions and life-threatening situations for participants in the educational process;
- lack of flexibility and adaptability of the educational process and controlling to the current situation in society;
- disconnection of the education system from institutional foundations;
- imperfect system of training of scientific and pedagogical staff without taking into account the needs of the labor market;
- shortage of qualified specialists, loss of interest in specialties and limited professional competencies;
- outdated educational and methodological support and imperfect interconnection of science and education;
- lack of important mechanisms necessary for the quality implementation of the educational process;
- closeness of educational institutions and low level of interdependence and interconnection between the subjects of educational activities;
- lack of systematic process of forming a real professional personnel reserve with promising employment [1, p. 6–22].

First of all, it is necessary to define the principles and mechanisms for ensuring the quality of higher education that are inherent in higher education institutions. The main principles of higher education quality are: accessibility and continuity, dignity (human/professional), equality and objectivity, priority and independence, scientific nature of higher education and integration of the relationship with science and stakeholders, flexibility, unity, diversity of education, fairness and impartiality, systematicity, etc. [2, p. 54–59].

The most important mechanisms for ensuring a full-fledged educational process are:

1) mechanism for ensuring the functioning of the educational environment. Ensuring the safety and comfort of the educational process, completeness of the infrastructure of higher education institutions, creating conditions for the safe use of digital technologies, applying the latest approaches to adaptation and integration of participants in the educational process, forming an inclusive educational space, ensuring the completeness of the relationship and interdependence between stakeholders and educational institutions, forming a learning, developmental and motivating educational space;

2) mechanism for assessing the quality of education. Publication of criteria, rules and procedures for assessing the academic achievements of higher education students; implementation of a cyclical analysis of learning outcomes, formation of the level of self-responsibility for learning outcomes and the ability of higher education students to self-assess, implementation of a system of fairness and objectivity of learning outcomes assessment;

3) mechanism for organizing the educational process. The use of modern approaches to the organization of the educational process in order to master key competencies and implement individual trajectories of students, the use of educational resources and digital technologies in the educational process (presentations, videos, social networks and channels, gamification), systematic professional development of teaching staff, taking into account modern requirements for the educational process in higher education institutions, organization of interaction between students and participants in educational activities on the basis of academic integrity;

4) mechanism for managing educational activities. Formation and implementation of strategies, goals and objectives of a higher education institution, planning and monitoring of its performance, taking into account development programs, creating a comfortable environment for ensuring the quality of higher education, publishing information about the activities of higher education institutions, making effective management decisions based on cooperation and interaction of participants in the educational process, uniform academic load in accordance with the age characteristics of higher education students, favorable activity and initiative to academic integrity [3; 4, p. 141–145].

Today, it is necessary to focus the educational process not only on the acquisition of «traditional» basic knowledge and skills, but also on the self-development and self-improvement of students, taking into account the latest knowledge and skills that are effectively applied in practice. This is due to the fact that the quality of the educational process is proportional to the high quality of the learning outcome, and changes in the educational process in higher education institutions require modernization of requirements and criteria for the quality of learning by students during their studies. The main criteria for the quality of higher education are: criteria for the quality of the educational process (formation of high potential of participants in the educational process, educational and methodological support of educational laboratories, rational use of educational and technological resources); criteria for the quality of the educational process (content resource provision, implementation of projects/programs/grants, formation of academic mobility for participants in the educational process); quality criteria for the formation of values of the educational process (creation of equal opportunities for students in obtaining higher education, ensuring guarantees for professional self-realization of participants in educational activities); quality criteria for learning outcomes (level of professional competencies, stakeholder satisfaction with the level of training, integration of higher education into the European educational space) [4, p. 141–145].

Comparing the traditional methodology for assessing the quality of higher education with international approaches, it can be argued that additional criteria should be taken into account to assess the quality of higher education: research productivity, prospects and opportunities for student employment, the level of cooperation and transfer of innovative technologies (knowledge, know-how, commercialization of ideas), joint scientific performance of participants in the educational process [4, p. 141–145]. The introduction of a system of higher education quality criteria contributes to the achievement of high quality educational services to meet the needs and requirements of stakeholders, to gain recognition for the high level of students' competencies from society, to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of optimizing educational activities, to create new opportunities and prospects in the market of educational services.

According to the British agency Times Higher Education, in 2023, this agency included 1591 universities from 112 countries in the ranking of the world's best higher education institutions, including 32 Ukrainian universities. Ukraine's higher education institutions are adapting to the current conditions, taking into account global European standards for assessing the quality of education and modernizing the educational process in accordance with the requirements of society and employers. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the global experience of the world's leading countries in improving the quality of higher education. Education in the United States is considered the best and highest quality in the world. After all, U.S. universities occupy leading positions in global rankings. At the same time, American education has its advantages (a huge selection of courses and specialties; the ability to realize one's own potential through programs/projects/grants/scholarships aimed at the self-development of higher education students; flexibility of higher education and diversity of study programs; the prospect of co-authorship with first-class researchers; unlimited opportunities for academic connections and cooperation) and disadvantages (different standards of higher education; high cost of education; limited credit programs for financing education; difficult standards for admission to universities; limited social guarantees) [5, p. 24–36; 6, p. 1–3].

Despite the high cost of education, the American education system offers a variety of opportunities for self-development and self-improvement, professional and academic growth, and encourages self-sufficiency. Although American education is not highly diversified, it offers opportunities for integration and recognition around the world.

The quality of higher education in Ukraine is seen as the efficient functioning and effective implementation of the educational process that meets international and European standards of higher education, provides higher education students with new knowledge and skills, taking into account the current needs of the labor market. In order to improve the quality of higher education in Ukraine, the most effective ways have been identified, namely:

Firstly, ensuring complete safety for the lives of participants in educational activities (arrangement of special shelters and bomb shelters for students and employees of higher education institutions, implementation of a cybersecurity system);

Secondly, increase the maintenance of the material and technical base of higher education institutions (implementation of budget programs for the development of higher education institutions, provision of preferential loans for higher education students to pay for educational services, introduction of digital platforms and innovative technologies to improve

distance learning and ensure closer communication between participants in the educational process);

Thirdly, creation of a system for monitoring and controlling the employment of graduates of higher education institutions (profiling of state orders, reorientation of specialties to the requirements of society and labor markets, intensification of foreign language learning, exchange between students and teachers within international programs/projects/grants);

Fourth, modernization of the mechanisms of regulatory and legal support of higher education institutions (amendments to the provisions on accreditation of educational programs, updating the methodology for assessing the quality of higher education);

Fifth, strengthening the responsibility of higher education institutions (transparency of the process of ensuring the quality of higher education, high level of professional qualification of teachers, fair distribution of educational resources, flexibility and mobility of educational content, academic independence);

Sixth, establishing close relationships and effective interaction between higher education institution and various institutions (expanding partnerships with stakeholders in training and professional development of students, participation of students in regional/state development programs);

Seventh, the development of inclusive education (individualized training programs, provision of material and methodological materials for people with special educational needs, organization of academic mobility and involvement of people with special educational needs in scientific and educational activities).

Conclusions. Thus, the quality of higher education depends on the current conditions and it must meet the interests and potential of its students and the requirements of the labor market. Assessment of the quality of higher education should be determined based on the final result of the educational services provided and can be measured on the basis of a system of criteria (level of foreign language proficiency, the share of employed graduates and their relevance to the acquired specialty, the number of students involved in research/programs/grants, etc.) These criteria will help assess the effectiveness of the acquired professional knowledge for graduates of higher education institutions. Higher education institutions should introduce the latest models of organizing the educational process, spread the practice of teaching disciplines in foreign languages and apply the areas of implementation to self-analysis of educational activities.

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